

Universal Pulses Enable a One-Hour Clinical Neuroimaging Protocol at Submillimeter Resolution on the NextGen 7T

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Synopsis

Motivation: Clinical imaging protocols of structural abnormalities stand to benefit from implementation of Universal Pulses (UP) in high-resolution whole-brain MRI at 7T.

Goals: To avoid the need for real-time patient-specific calibration and RF pulse tailored computations, UPs can provide data-trained pulse profiles tailored to sequence and coil while preserving efficacy across subjects.

Approach: Field maps were collected on 6 subjects and used as training data to design RF pulses for 3D anatomical sequences in a clinical scanning protocol for epilepsy patients.

Results: This work successfully demonstrates UP implementation for a clinical imaging protocol of adults and children on the Berkeley NextGen 7T scanner.

Impact: Universal Pulses provide a seamless solution to mitigate the RF field inhomogeneity problem for neuro MRI at 7T, enabling clinical populations to benefit from fast, high-resolution anatomical imaging without the need for dielectric pads.

Main Abstract

Introduction: Imaging at ultra-high field (UHF) strengths has significant advantages for increased SNR and resolution, but continues to pose challenges in the development of applications accessible to clinical populations. Specifically, UHF imaging is known to suffer from B1+ field inhomogeneities that cause a non-recoverable signal loss in important regions such as the temporal lobes and cerebellum. These artifacts impose limitations on post-processing procedures that directly affect the quantitative and diagnostic value of data, making routine clinical imaging UHF inaccessible to populations that would benefit from resolution difficult to obtain at 3T.

Universal Pulses (UPs)¹ involve the collection of fieldmaps beforehand on a representative sample of the population, and optimize the RF pulse profiles offline simultaneously on all subjects in the database, with the returned solution inserted into the MR sequences seamlessly. The NextGen 7T scanner² is a significant technological advancement to achieve higher resolution combining multiple elements - high-performance Impulse head gradient (amplitude 200mT/m, slew rate 900mT/m/ms) in addition to 16Tx and 128Rx capabilities. The goal of this work was to design and implement UP for anatomical sequences with the 8Tx-64Rx RF coil on the NextGen scanner, and to demonstrate its utility in clinical protocols.

Methods: To design nonselective pTx UP design at 7T, B1 and B0 fieldmaps were collected on 6 subjects and used as training data to design RF pulses and modify the following sequences: MPRAGE, MP2RAGE, and T2 SPACE (FLAIR). All data were collected on the UC Berkeley 7T NexGen scanner (MAGNETOM Terra; Siemens Healthineers, Erlangen, Germany). Each sequence was evaluated on healthy controls with and without UPs. The inversion, excitation and refocusing pTx UPs were each designed using the kT-point method³ under explicit power and SAR constraints. The transmit k-space trajectory was optimized simultaneously with the complex RF coefficients. Because of non-convexity, 8 optimizations were run in parallel with different random k-space trajectory initializations while the RF solutions were initialized using the variable exchange method⁴. Whole-brain 3D T1 (0.75mm, T/10:33m), T2 (Res/0.55mm, T/9:45min), T2 FLAIR (0.7mm, T/6:34min) UP images were collected in adults and children as part of a clinical epilepsy protocol, along with (non UP), whole brain QSM 3D (0.4mm, T/9:47m) or T2*(0.3mm in-plane, 1mm-thick, T/4:07min), multi-shell multiband diffusion MRI (0.9mm, T/7:26m) and multiband functional MRI (0.8mm, T/20m), which can be completed within one hour. An optional SWI was also collected. All patients or their legal guardians gave written informed consent, with verbal assent also obtained from minors, in accordance with an approved IRB protocol at UC Berkeley.

Results: Bloch simulations (Fig. 1) returned normalized root mean square performance over the 6 subjects database equal to 3.6%, 7.3%, 11.3% for the inversion, small excitation and refocusing pulses respectively. The high-slew rate capability (900mT/m/ms) of the gradient coil contributed to the performance of the RF pulse by allowing larger k-space jumps from one kT point to the next during the short gradient blips. 3D T1 MP2RAGE acquisitions comparing both UPs versus CP mode pulses in a healthy control are shown in Fig. 2 with dramatic improvements in signal artifacts at the posterior fossa. The 3D T2 SPACE and 3D T2 FLAIR acquisitions shown in Figs. 3-5 demonstrate that UPs in the one-hour clinical protocol recovered homogeneous excitations and contrasts in posterior regions of the occipital lobes and cerebellum, including CSF suppression down to the cervical spinal cord, as well as challenging regions of the temporal lobes, enabling excellent delineation of mesoscale intracortical anatomic features and pathology in pediatric and adult patients. We found very infrequently, the CSF suppression was incomplete, e.g. in Fig. 3B.

Discussion and Conclusion: Despite major improvements made over the years, implementation of pTx remains complex and we have found UP sequences to be reliably integrated into clinical imaging protocols. This work seeks to contribute reliable high resolution protocols aimed at correcting image nonuniformity present at UHF and demonstrates the utility of UP for both clinical and research applications. The incomplete CSF suppression has been previously reported as an effect varying across scanners that is possibly due to CSF flow and is currently under investigation.

In conclusion, we demonstrate that UPs enable high-quality whole-brain 3D imaging at submillimeter resolution on the NexGen 7T scanner for a clinical epilepsy protocol obtained within an hour in both adults and children.

Acknowledgements

Research supported by the BRAIN Initiative (National Institutes of Health (NIH) grants U01-EB025162, U24-NS129949), NIH R44-MH129278, and H2020 FET Open AROMA (885876). Support from Weill NeuroHub and from the Chancellor's Office of UC Berkeley.

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Tables and Figures

Figure 1. Bloch simulations of the flip angle induced by the universal pulses designed for the a) T2-SPACE 105° refocusing and b) 180° inversion pulses on the 8Tx-64Rx NextGen scanner. Comparison of circularly polarized pulses (c) and universal pulses (d) with 3D T2-SPACE.

Figure 2. Comparison of circularly polarized pulses (top) and universal pulses (bottom) with MP2RAGE in healthy controls.

Figure 3. A) Left: Coronal 0.55mm isotropic 3D T2 SPACE with UP in an adult epilepsy patient showing mesoscale intracortical features such as the stria of Gennari (dark band) within V1 primary visual cortex (arrows). **Right:** Midline sagittal 0.8mm isotropic 3D T2 FLAIR with UP in a child with epilepsy showing folia and fissures of the cerebellar vermis with excellent CSF suppression down to the upper cervical spinal cord. **B)** 0.8mm isotropic 3D T2 FLAIR with UP in an adult epilepsy patient.

Figure 4. 0.55mm isotropic 3D T2 SPACE with UPs on an adult epilepsy patient showing exquisite delineation of the internal architecture of the hippocampal head, body and tail (arrows), including curvilinear dark lamina corresponding to the stratum radiatum/lacunosum/moleculare.

Figure 5. 0.55mm isotropic 3D T2 SPACE with UPs in a child with epilepsy with a tiny left lateral middle temporal gyrus hemorrhage (circles) along the residual track of a previously placed depth electrode.